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**REACHABILITY IN ATTACKER-DEFENDER GAMES WITH DIFFERENT
ARENAS**

By

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ABSTRACT

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Recreational activities help us to grow as people. Often, the origins of games may be traced in the real world. We deal with a variety of games, and most of them necessitate the construction or design of an arena in which the game must be performed to determine the winner of the game. The Robot Game is a two-person integer lattice vector addition game in which one player, Eve (Attacker), attempts to reach origin or the target configuration while the other, Adam (Defender), attempts to stop Eve from reaching the origin. The game is played in turns with defender starting the game always and ending with attacker's move. The problem is judging if Eve has an effective strategy to win the game. The main computational difficulty is evaluating whether Eve has a winning strategy for getting to the goal configuration from the base configuration, or if Adam can prevent the objective from being achieved. The game has several versions, and many of the versions in dimension two are indecipherable. Constrained versions, such as restricted area and shifting goal functions, was considered in this study to determine the winning technique in dimension two, with the possibility of addressing multidimensional space. There was no winning strategy discovered in various attacker-defender games played on different mathematical domains with varied transformations (moves). In this thesis, we explored three variations of the game played on 2 dimension. In first case, we considered a scenario where defender has no move, or he has a single zero move, but attacker has normal moves. In second case we looked at the variation with a single nonzero move of the defender and he can apply it at any certain point in the game of his choice along with normal moves of the attacker. The third case is the

situation where the game is played in turns and defender has multiple moves like attacker. We took a unique approach to determine the path that might help Eve to reach her destination to have a winning strategy.

DECLARATION

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I confirm that I have acted honestly, ethically, and professionally in conduct leading to assessment for the programme of study.

I confirm that I have not copied material from another source nor committed plagiarism nor fabricated data when completing the attached piece of work.

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Chapter 1. INTRODUCTION

Tic-tac-toe, chess, go, and video games are examples of recreational activities that assist us to improve ourselves. The beginnings of games are frequently found in the real world. Chess and battleships are abstractions of combat, but Monopoly is an abstraction of the economics and wealth production (2018). The real world plays an important part in the development of games. There are several types of games that we face, and most of them need the building or design of an arena inside which the game must be played. It is one of the most common computational concerns in games to see if one of the participants can dominate the fight regardless of what the opponent does. To put it another way, it is to be decided whether the game has a winning strategy. Verifying the plausibility of a winning strategy in multiple high-dimensional and low-dimensional games may be computationally difficult, if not impossible.

1.1 Scope

Firstly, the dissertation gives a brief idea about robot games and how the game is supposed to be played explaining the rules and regulations of the game. The dissertation then goes on explaining the different variations of the game mentioned. It then goes on explaining three sub cases of the attacker defender game played on dimension two within a defined area. Algorithms and manual experimentation of the steps and approach are also provided in future chapters which will help understand how a robot game with constraints can be played. Also provided are the coordinate plane simulation of the examples provided for the subcases to give an illustration. The dissertation also covers a lot of past work on different types of attacker-defender

games that are played on different dimensions. Other dimension games, which are outside the scope of this thesis, are not covered in depth.

Some discussion on how strategies similar to robot games play a vital role in industries as well as everyday life is also mentioned.

1.2 Problem Statement

Robot games are two-player games in which a vector of n integer counters is updated. This thesis will look at a two-player vector addition game in an integer lattice \mathbb{Z}^n (n -dimensional integer grid). Both players have vectors, and each turn, the player's selected vector is added to the game's current configuration vector. We call the game as *Attacker-Defender* games. An Attacker-Defender game is played in rounds, with each round beginning with a move by the Defender and ending with a move by the Attacker. Attacker's (Eve) goal is to get to a target location, while Defender's (Adam) goal is to prevent Attacker from getting there. Then, if Attacker can finally achieve the target position i.e., to reach the zero vector regardless of Defender's maneuvers, we claim she has a successful winning strategy (2018). The primary computational challenge we investigate is determining which of the players wins given a set of valid moves, a computing environment, and reachability goals. Based on (Doyen *et.al.*, 2013), the game starts from an initial configuration between two players $x_0 \in \mathbb{Z}^2$. Player 2 selects a vector $v \in V$ in each turn, followed by player 1 selecting a vector $u \in U$. The following round's configuration becomes $x + v + u$. The goal of one of the players is to reach a target or $(0,0)$ configuration and the combination in which the player reaches that configuration is known as winning configuration.

There are several permutations of the game, and it has been observed that most variations in dimension two are indecisive (Doyen *et.al.*, 2013). The project's purpose is to examine restricted forms of the game that have more efficient solutions, in which the game's area is constrained to a certain region or the objective function may be adjusted by adding various numerical constraints. The variant in which a defender may only employ one move during play and must renounce the others was studied in this study. Also discussed is the circumstance in which the defender has no move, resulting in the creation of a tree with exclusively attacker movements.

Figure 1 : Representation of the game

Attacker (Eve) denoted as • and Defender (Adam) denoted as O. An ideal winning strategy will lead Eve to origin irrespective of the moves by Adam (2016).

1.3 Approach

Attacker-Defender games are turn-based robot games in which two players compete against one other. During early stages our approach was to explore the related research required to understand the concept of robot games and gaining knowledge

on different variations of the game and how they are played, as discussed in the later chapters. Among the different variations of the game, we considered the variation of game in dimension 2 only. Particularly out of the different types of robot games including matrix game, word game, braid game and vector addition games, our thesis is based upon the vector addition game only . We investigated a few variations of the attacker-defender game in dimension two in this thesis and discussed how to locate successful situations as well as the challenges associated with doing so. We considered variations where players' resources are limited to certain extent and the game to be played within a defined arena. The game was played in a memoryless strategy meaning the player does not have to recall the previous move to make a future move. Three subcases of the game were studied, and high-level algorithms were analyzed including their time complexities and stopping condition. During the development phase we took the approach of playing the game manually on a grid paper for the three variations of the game. The game was simulated on the grid paper with given user input, and we used the backtracking approach to develop a tree with the moves of the players starting with the target configuration as discussed in later chapters. Then we developed a basic code for a subcase of the robot game using backtracking and high-level pseudocode for the remaining subcases.

1.4 Outcome

Previous study into robot games gave me a strong grasp of the many varieties of robot games. Matrix games, word games, braid games, and simple vector addition games may all be played using game theory. The vector addition game, especially the two-dimensional vector addition game, was the subject of our thesis. There are several variations of the vector addition game, including one-dimensional, two-dimensional,

and three-dimensional variants and higher. This thesis's main outcome was to analyze and develop high level algorithms for restricted versions of the two-dimension robot games and determine if one of them has any winning strategy. The condition that was followed during the analysis was that the game must be played within a defined arena meaning the game must be played within a specific region or area. We looked at restricted version of the game where the players' moves were limited in different cases and developed high level algorithms that will achieve the players to have a winning strategy using a path containing the good points that will help them reach their target configuration from the initial configuration. The thesis also helped developed manual representation of the robot game during initial phase to understand the basic gameplay. It helped generate algorithms that can be used in future purpose for anyone exploring more versions of the game and trying to develop any software.

Chapter 2. BACKGROUND AND REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Related Work and Literature

Two players, a reacher and an opponent, update a vector of m integer counters to play robot games (Doyen *et.al.*, 2013). In Z^m , each player is in charge of a finite number of integer vectors. The game begins with a given initial vector of counter values, $v_0 \in Z_m$, and proceeds in rounds. In each round, the reacher adds a vector from his set to the counter values first, then the opponent. When the reacher's vector of counter values is 0 at the end of his turn, he wins. In (Arul *et.al.*, 2013), an algorithm is provided for solving robot games on integer line in EXPTIME. A theorem is provided which suggests that determining if the reacher has a winning strategy from x_0 in a one-dimensional robot game with $V = \{0\}$ and a starting counter value x_0 is NP-complete. The algorithm discussed in the paper can determine the winning set in exponential time which is already proven by correctness and termination.

Algorithm 1: Algorithm for solving robot games on the integer line.

```

Data: A robot game  $(U, V)$ .
Result: A description of the winning set.
/* Require: Functions computing the sets we use, as defined in the
Section 4. */
begin
   $d \leftarrow 0$ 
   $X \leftarrow \text{Pre}(\{0\}) \cup \{0\}$  /* to avoid handling  $\text{gcd}(\{0\})$  in the first step */
  if  $X = \{0\}$  then return  $X$ 

  /* Step 1. */
  while  $d = 0$  do
     $d' \leftarrow \text{gcd}(X)$ 
     $I \leftarrow I_{(U,V)}(X)$ 
    /*  $I$  is a set of  $X$ -reachable counter values with a large absolute
value */
     $Y \leftarrow \text{Pre}(I \cap d'\mathbb{Z})$ 
    /* From  $Y$ , the reacher can force the next round to end at a counter
value known to be winning */
    if  $Y \setminus d'\mathbb{Z} \neq \emptyset$  then  $X \leftarrow X \cup \{\min(Y \setminus d'\mathbb{Z})\}$  /* minimum in absolute value */
    else  $d \leftarrow d'$  /* We know that  $d$  is  $\text{gcd}(\text{Win})$ : we exit the loop */

  /* Step 2. */
  if  $X \not\subseteq \mathbb{N} \wedge X \not\subseteq -\mathbb{N}$  then return  $d\mathbb{Z}$  /* Lemma 7 */
  else
     $I \leftarrow \text{Ampl}(U, V)$ 
     $b \leftarrow \hat{F}(X)$ 
    if  $X \subseteq \mathbb{N}$  then
      if  $-\mathbb{N} \cap \text{Pre}(I \cap d\mathbb{N}) \neq \emptyset$  then return  $d\mathbb{Z}$  /* Lemma 7, second try */
      else  $\text{Unbd} \leftarrow \{x \in d\mathbb{Z} \mid x > b\}$  /* Half-line of winning counter values */
    else
      if  $\mathbb{N} \cap \text{Pre}(I \cap -d\mathbb{N}) \neq \emptyset$  then return  $d\mathbb{Z}$ 
      else  $\text{Unbd} \leftarrow \{x \in d\mathbb{Z} \mid x < b\}$ 
     $G \leftarrow \text{Restr}_d^b(U, V)$ 
    /* Between 0 and  $b$ , we compute the attractor on the restricted arena
according to Proposition 5 */
    return  $\text{Unbd} \cup \text{RestrAttr}(G)$ 

```

Figure 2 : Algorithm for Solving Robot games on integer line (Arul et al., 2013)

Table 1 : Results in Dimension 1

Semantics	Vectors in	Complexity
VASS	$\{-1, 0, 1\}$	PSPACE-COMplete
VASS	\mathbb{Z}	EXPTIME-hard, EXPSPACE
Z	$\{-1, 0, 1\}$	PSPACE-COMplete
Z	\mathbb{Z}	EXPTIME-hard, EXPSPACE
NBVASS	$\{-1, 0, 1\}$	PSPACE-COMplete
NBVASS	\mathbb{Z}	EXPTIME-hard, EXPSPACE

(Halava et al., 2015)

In counter reachability games, Eve wants to go to the origin, whilst Adam tries to stay away from it. It was seen that when moves are multidimensional (matrices and pair of

words), the attacker defender games are undecidable whereas, when the moves are one-dimensional (integers and binary words) it is decidable (2018). It can be observed (2018) that in *VAS games in two-dimension*, where the arena is confined to the positive quadrant Z^{+2} , it is undecided if Eve has a winning strategy. It's a type of counter reachability game in which the graph has just two vertices. In the same paper the *two-dimensional VASS games (2- dimensional game on integer vector addition system with states)*, which are an extension of VAS games in which the participants have control states, are also discussed before considering the decidability of the VAS games . Eve has a winning strategy in the situation that the machine achieves a configuration where both counters are zero. Another variation of the Z- VASS games is played with players' moves consisting of integers that modify the counter. This is known as a *one-dimensional VASS* game. This version has also been proven to be EXPSPACE-complete. It is likewise uncertain if Eve has a successful approach in a *two-dimensional integer VAS (integer vector addition system)* game by building a Z^2 -VAS game simulating the Z^2 -VASS game (2018). Based on (Halava *et.al.*, 2015, March) for degree two robot games of any dimension n , the issue can be solved in polynomial time.

Table 2 : Results in Dimension 2

Semantics	Vectors in	Complexity
VASS	$\{-1,0,1\}^2$	Undecidable
Z	$\{-1,0,1\}^2$	Undecidable
NBVASS	$\{-1,0,1\}^2$	Undecidable

(Halava *et.al.*, 2015)

In (2018), two variations of Z^d -VASS games in which players' resources are constrained were considered. Control Z^d -VASS games with *safety objective for Adam* to use his move only K times and must avoid otherwise. Control Z^d -VASS games with *reachability objective for Eve* to use her move only K times and must avoid otherwise.

Based on lemma in (Halava *et.al.*, 2015, March), attacker can win a game if and only if $v_1' + u' = v_2'$ and $a = -kv_2'$ or $v_2' + u' = v_1'$ and $a = -kv_1'$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Attacker's set $U: \{u_1, u_2\}$, Defender's set $V: \{v_1, v_2\}$.

Figure 3 : Illustration of the lemma above.

In (Halava *et.al.*, 2015) below sets of equations are provided to determine the winning strategy for attacker. Let $u_1 = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$, $u_2 = (\beta_1, \beta_2)$, $v_1 = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$, $v_2 = (\delta_1, \delta_2)$. Let $U = \{u_1, u_2\}$ and $V = \{v_1, v_2\}$ be Attacker's and Defender's vector sets, respectively and an initial vector $a = (a_1, a_2)$. The following equations need to be satisfied for attacker to win the game, where $x, y, z, w \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$\begin{aligned} x\alpha_1 + y\beta_1 + z\gamma_1 + w\delta_1 + a_1 &= 0 \\ x\alpha_2 + y\beta_2 + z\gamma_2 + w\delta_2 + a_2 &= 0 \quad \& \quad (x + y) - (z + w) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Ethical Use of Data and Industry Relevance

To design, analysis and predict the behavior of several actors that interact with each other throughout the decision - making processes, game theory has a vital role. Players conduct acts according with the provided "rules of the game," and these combined activities produce ultimate outcomes and payoffs, according to game theory (Chatterjee *et.al.*, 2001). Aside from offering a framework for modelling competitive situations, game theory goes a long way toward addressing the essential question: What is the best option or action a competitor should take while predicting the best actions of their competitors? There are many companies in a supply chain (SC) owned and managed by various parties and they each take decisions that are consistent with their own vision and mission (Erhun *et.al.*,2003). The selected actions of the SC players in all decentralized systems may not always provide the "best" result if the supply chain is seen as a single entity. Since every player is self-interested, we typically see software inefficiencies, i.e., results are different than when a single decision maker handled the system "optimally" and was able for those players to make decisions and enforce the type of behavior that this optimal solution globally (or centrally) dictates.

The data needed to conduct the trials to arrive at a winning strategy are integer values from the number system. As a result, no extra data including human data is necessary to complete this project or come to any conclusion.

Chapter 3. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

The goal of this study was to look at a few situations of the attacker defender game, considering the open undecidable challenges connected with 2-dimensional VAS Attacker-Defender games. We'll try to find out the memoryless winning approach by looking for interesting patterns in winning spots, starting with small values, and working our way up to larger amounts. Attacker-Defender games are turn-based games in which two players compete against one other. We investigated a few variations of the attacker-defender game in dimension two in this report. We discussed how to locate successful situations as well as the challenges associated with doing so. We considered variations where players' resources are limited to certain extent. So far, the Attacker-Defender games looked at have been either undecidable in dimension 2 or belong to high-complexity classes like EXPTIME or EXPSPACE.

3.1 Identifying & Analyzing subcases

We look at three variations of the 2D-VAS games in which players' resources or movements are constrained.

3.1.1 Case 1 : Game with no move or a (0,0) move of the Defender

In this case, we're looking at the attacker's actions and path without the presence of a defender move. This simulation will just seek for the attacker's winning situations since the defender's movement will not be considered. Considering attacker move as $u = (u_1, u_2)$. We take the inverse of the move as $u' = (-u_1, -u_2)$. The final(target) configuration will be the origin i.e., $o = (0, 0)$ which must be reached by attacker to have a winning strategy.

We start at the final configuration and travel back up to a specific level utilizing the inverse of the attacker's move when employing the backtracking technique.

As an example, let us consider attacker's move $u = (2, 1)$. So, the inverse of the move will be $u' = (-2, -1)$. Now based on the backtracking approach. We will start adding the inverse of the move to the final configuration i.e., $o = (0, 0)$ and go backwards such that it does not cross the boundary. And the set of moves for backtracking from origin will be $\{(-2, -1), (-4, -2), (-6, -3), (-8, -4), (-10, -5), (-12, -6), (-14, -7), (-16, -8), (-18, -10)\}$.

Figure 4 : Illustration of Case 1 on Coordinate plane

If the initial point is one of the points from the set or we somehow reach those points from other points and apply the attacker's move (\mathbf{u}) and keep iterating with \mathbf{u} , we will reach the origin or target configuration and state that the attacker has a winning strategy from the points indicated in the backtracking set. Otherwise considering the points from the set achieved, if the starting point or any point leading to those points

not in the set will lead to a losing strategy for the attacker as it will not reach the target configuration.

Input : Attacker move $u=(u1,u2)$, Defender Move $v=(0,0)$, target position $(0,0)$, and arena = $[p, r]$

Output : Determining whether attacker has a winning strategy or not.

1. If u and v within the defined arena, then:

- 1. foreach element (u,v) do $u'=(-u1,-u2)$**
- 2. Start backtracking with attacker move from the target and store in x .**
- 3. If x within arena continue and make a tree of winning positions and store them in a set.**
 - 1. Then add v to any of the points from the set and add u' to the new point generated.**
 - 2. Check If the new points generated within arena, then check new points in the previous set, we say attacker has a winning strategy otherwise not.**
 - 3. Else Exit game**
- 4. Else exit game**

2. Else exit game as it is out of the defined arena.

Algorithm 3.1.1: Solving a game with a zero or no defender move.

First, we demonstrate that the algorithm is valid. At the start of the game, we verify if the moves are in the designated area in line 1. Otherwise, we exit the game. If affirmative, we go to the following stage, which will serve as a loop. We start with each element of the defender move and we keep moving forward. We take the inverse of the moves u' . We start backtracking from the target point meaning we add the inverse u' move to the target point or $(0,0)$ generating new point and storing it in x . We make sure to check whether the new point generated is within the defined arena or not in line 3. If it is out of the defined arena, we exit the game. Otherwise, we add the u' to the new point generated. We keep checking each point generated to be within the arena. If not within the defined arena, we exit the game. We keep adding u' to the new point generated, to make a tree of the points made of only attackers move. Considering the defender skips his move, we will end up with the tree produced by backtracking using the attacker's move. If we add the attacker move (u) to any point on the tree and

iterate from the initial configuration we will reach the target configuration creating a path from the initial to target configuration giving attacker, the winning strategy.

The algorithm will terminate as described above when it is out of the defined arena. In this case, there are $kp+k$ calls in total to solve the reachability problem. As a result, it is possible to solve it in non-deterministic polynomial time.

3.1.2 Case 2 : Game with a single non-zero move of the Defender

In this case, we're looking at the attacker's actions and path with the presence of a single defender move. This simulation will seek for the attacker's winning situations based on the single defender move which he can apply at any position. Considering attacker move as $u = (u_1, u_2)$. and the defender move $v = (v_1, v_2)$. We take the inverse of the moves as $u' = (-u_1, -u_2)$ and $v' = (-v_1, -v_2)$. The final(target) configuration will be the origin i.e., $o = (0,0)$ which must be reached by attacker irrespective of the single defender move to have a winning strategy.

Considering Attacker's move = (1,3) and Defender's move = (2,1) we simulated the play to certain level. Based on back tracking approach starting from target configuration $o = (0,0)$ like the previous case it was seen that the winning set for attacker was $\{(-1, -3), (-2, -6), (-3, -9), (-4, -12), (-5, -15), (-6, -18), (-7, -21)\}$. And by applying defender's inverse move on each point on the set it was seen that the moves of attacker were not in the winning set of the attacker and. It shows that (2, 1) is a good move for Defender as it will move attacker away from reaching the origin. In an ideal scenario for attacker to have a winning strategy, irrespective of defender's move on attackers winning set, the new points generated should be same as the winning set.

Figure 5 : Illustration of Case 2 in the form of a tree

This algorithm will explain how we can achieve the winning positions of the attacker using the backtracking approach where defender has a single move and can apply it only once and at any time in the game.

Input : Attacker move $u=(u_1,u_2)$, Defender Move $v=(v_1,v_2)$,target position $(0,0)$, and arena = $[p, r]$

Output : Determining whether attacker has a winning strategy or not.

1. If u and v within the defined arena, then:

- 1. foreach** element (u,v) do $u'=(-u_1,-u_2)$ and $v' = (-v_1,-v_2)$
- 2. Start backtracking** with attacker move from the target and store in x .
- 3. If x within arena** continue and make a tree of winning positions like the previous case and store them in a set.
 - 1. Then add v'** to any of the points from the set and add u' to the new point generated.
 - 2. Check If** the new points generated within arena, then check new points in the previous set ,we say attacker has a winning strategy otherwise not.
 - 3. Else** Exit game
- 4. Else** exit game

2. Else exit game as it is out of the defined arena.

Algorithm 3.1.2: Solving a game with single non-zero defender move.

First, we demonstrate that this algorithm is valid. We check if the moves are in the appropriate region in line 1 at the start of the game. Otherwise, we'll be forced to leave the game. If yes, we go to the next stage, which will act as a loop. We begin with each component of the defender move and progress forward. We take the inverse of the moves u' . We start backtracking from the target point meaning we add the inverse u' move to the target point or $(0,0)$ generating new point and storing it in x . In line 3, we ensure that the new point formed is within the defined area or not. We exit the game if it is outside of the designated arena. Otherwise, we append the u' to the newly created point. We keep an eye on each produced point to make sure it's still within the arena. We quit the game if we are not within the set arena. We keep adding u' to each new point formed, forming a tree of solely attackers moving points. Considering the defender apply his move only once in the entire game but at any point we will see there will be situations where we will come back to the attacker winning set and having a path to the target point giving attacker the winning strategy.

The algorithm will terminate as described above when it is out of the defined arena. there are $kp+k$ calls in total to solve the reachability problem. As a result, it is possible to solve it in non-deterministic polynomial time.

3.1.3 Case 3 : Game with multiple non-zero moves of the Defender

In this case, we're looking at the attacker's actions and path without the presence of a defender move. This simulation will just seek for the attacker's winning situations since the defender's movement will not be considered. Considering attacker moves as $u = \{(u_1, u_2), (u_3, u_4)\}$ and $v = \{(v_1, v_2), (v_3, v_4)\}$. We take the inverse of both the moves as $u' = \{(-u_1, -u_2), (-u_3, -u_4)\}$ and $v = \{(-v_1, -v_2), (-v_3, -v_4)\}$. The final(target) configuration will be the origin i.e., $o = (0,0)$ which must be reached by attacker to have a winning strategy.

Figure 6 : Illustration of Case 3 in the form of a tree

We start at the final configuration and travel back up to a specific level without going out from the defined arena utilizing the inverse of the attacker's move when employing the backtracking technique. We need to determine a path that will lead us to the target configuration giving us a winning strategy for the attacker.

As an example, if we consider a point from the Figure 4, say $(-4, -12)$ from there the defender will have two options to consider $u = \{(1,2), (0,4)\}$. As a thumb rule for the game defender will always start the game and the attacker's move will always end the game and the target configuration being $(0,0)$ in this case. Considering both options from defender the new points generated will be $x = \{(-3,-10), (-4,-8)\}$. The next turn being attacker's, she will have two options to play which is $v = \{(2,2), (3,0)\}$. Adding the moves of the attacker to x , the new points generated will be $x = \{(-1,-8), (-2,-6), (0,-10), (-1,-8)\}$. From the new points generated, the defender will apply his moves as the next turn will be his. After applying u to the points, the new x will be $\{(0,-6), (-1,-6), (-1,-4), (-2,-2), \dots, (-1,-4)\}$. Being the next turn attackers, she will apply v to apply to x and it will result in $x = \{(2,-4), (-1,-4), (0,0), \dots, (-1,-2), (-2,-4)\}$. The target configuration which is $(0,0)$ is present in the newly generated set of points after the simulation of the game for few levels. Therefore, the set of good points or as called an attractor in this simulation is $= \{(-4,12), (-4,-8), (-2,-6), (-2,-2)\}$. We can see a path made of the points in the attractor exists in Figure 5, and thus the attacker will have a winning strategy when both the players will play the exact points in turns. Similarly, this concept is applicable to the rest of the points on the illustrated tree in Figure 4 .

Figure 7 : Illustration of Case 3

If in any scenario in the illustrated tree in Figure 6, the defender chooses to play the points other than the points that is mentioned in the sets above, we will see that the attacker will be deviated from the path to the target configuration, and she will not be having the winning strategy. Such scenarios will be beneficial for the defender as he will be successful in making attacker avoid the target configuration and it can be said those points are bad points for attacker and a successful path does not exist.

Using the above concept of backtracking and adding the move of each player, we developed the below high-level algorithm that would lead us to the winning strategy of the attacker or defender depending on the path generated.

Input : Attacker move $u=(u_1,u_2)$, Defender Move $v=(v_1,v_2)$, target position $(0,0)$, and arena = $[p, r]$

Output : Determining whether attacker has a winning strategy or not.

1. If u and v within the defined arena, then:

1. **foreach** element (u,v) do $u' = (-u_1, -u_2)$ and $v' = (-v_1, -v_2)$
2. Start backtracking with attacker move's first and ending with defender's move at the last.
3. First node of the tree will be $(0,0) + (-u_1, -u_2)$ store in x
4. **If x in arena, then:**
 1. Second node of the tree will be $(0,0) + (-u_1, -u_2) + (-v_1, -v_2)$ update x
 2. And it will continue like $(0,0) + (-u_1, -u_2) + (-v_1, -v_2) + (-u_1, -u_2) + (-v_1, -v_2) \dots (-x, -y)$ till it does not cross the arena
 3. If from any point of the tree we find a path leading to the target configuration irrespective of defenders move, we say it will be a good point for the attacker.

5. Else exit.

2. Else exit game as it is out of the defined arena.

Algorithm 3.1.3: Solving a game with multiple non-zero defender moves.

First, we demonstrate that this algorithm is valid. We check if the moves are in the appropriate region in line 1 at the start of the game. Otherwise, we'll be forced to leave the game. If yes, we go to the next stage, which will act as a loop. We begin with each component of both the defender and attacker move and progress forward. We take the inverse of the moves u' and v' . We start backtracking from the target point meaning we add the inverse u' move to the target point or $(0,0)$ generating new point and storing it in x . In line 4, we ensure that the new point formed is within the defined area or not. We exit the game if it is outside of the designated arena. Otherwise, we append the v' to the newly created point. We keep an eye on each produced point to make sure it's still within the arena. We quit the game if we are not within the set arena. We keep adding $x+u'+v'$ to each new point formed, forming a tree of both attacker and defender points. As long as the points generated are within the defined arena, the algorithm will continue to run.

The algorithm for Case 3 will terminate when the points are out of the defined arena given as a user input. There are k^p+k calls in total to solve the reachability problem. As a result, it is possible to solve it in non-deterministic polynomial time.

3.2 Implementation And Evaluation

Several sophisticated circumstances in robot games were explored at the outset of the project, but it became clear as time went on that they were both outside the scope of the project and difficult to execute. Only one case of the two-dimensional robot game was studied and tested, and the code was created for only one of the cases; the remaining cases were manually analyzed and constructed using grid paper. A basic algorithm was discussed during the initial phase of the project and with time it was modified and developed for other more difficult cases also. At first, the case of no move for defender was implemented in code as well as manually, and it was seen that the code produced set of points that was good for the attacker as the defender has no moves to apply. The code was based on the backtracking approach discussed in previous chapters. It was seen during experiments that the points generated from the code are good points for the attacker as she can reach the target configuration using her normal move from the generated points. There exists a path from the generated points to reach the target configuration and so there exists a winning strategy for attacker whenever defender skips his move or applies the zero move.

For the case with a single defender move the similar approach was taken in determining the winning set of points for attacker and the points were generated within the defined arena which was represented as a tree on a grid paper. After getting the set of points the single defender was added to each point on the set to check whether

the same tree of points was getting generated or not. It was seen during experimenting that for few points of the defender the new tree generated was not similar to the tree previously generated with only attackers move using backtracking. This shows that the chosen set of moves by defender was good for him but not good for the attacker. The illustrations are shown above in the previous part in the form of a tree which shows the experiments done manually before developing the algorithm.

In the more complicated case with the multiple defender moves a similar approach of backtracking was taken and it was played as a turn based actual game starting with the attacker and ending with defender. Therefore, instead of creating a tree with only attacker move and then applying defender's move we must do one at a time. The tree representation denotes a few levels of simulation of the game before it goes out of the defined arena. It can be seen on the tree that there are winning or losing position for the attacker which involves the moves of the defender on several layers of the tree. Only the winning path or points are highlighted on the tree. Considering any points on the tree both the players have two options that they can play, depending on any of the choices it will be either a winning strategy for the attacker or the defender. The multiple tree representation of the game helped in developing the high-level algorithm.

Chapter 4. CONCLUSIONS

Because games are such an essential part of our daily lives and are also influenced by certain elements of our lives, it is a never-ending competition with only one winner it is difficult for the player to have a winning strategy without simulating the game. We deal with a variety of games, and most of them necessitate the construction or design of an arena in which the game must be performed. The ability of one of the participants to dominate the combat regardless of what the opponent does is one of the most common computational issues in games. In the versions of robot games addressed in this dissertation, establishing if one of the players has a winning strategy is the focus. We restricted the game to a certain specified arena, and the game will end if the players' moves leaves the arena. The game was simulated using a unique approach in which we analyzed the game starting from the target configuration and provided a high-level algorithm for three scenarios of the game.

4.1 Lessons Learned

Considering the previous research papers discussed in Chapter 2, it is seen that there are several versions of the robot games played on different dimensions which are not undecidable. In fact, they give a clear understanding how robot games can play important part in making decisions on day-to-day life as well in industries which are always full of competition and competitors. It helped developing a clear understanding on how to approach an unknown problem and how to deal with them with proper background research and understanding.

In fact, the algorithms for three different variants of the robot game mentioned are likely to be the thesis's key results. It provides a comprehensive grasp of the game

and how to decide the winning strategy, as well as the game's stopping circumstances and developing a concept for a path that would assist one of the players in winning the game. The thesis also provided some insights on how to develop high level pseudocodes from scratch based on certain requirements.

4.2 Prospects for Further Work

In future reports, the analysis can take into account the high-level pseudocodes for the three variations discussed in the thesis and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the achieving the winning strategy for different variations of the game. The unique approach of backtracking can also be considered while developing the software for different variations of the game. It will help develop a path and the winning strategy for the players. The algorithms developed in this thesis covers only their time complexity so in future reports the memory consumptions can also be taken into consideration and deliver the memory consumption along with time for the different versions of the game.

4.3 Risk Management

Risk is an unforeseen occurrence or circumstance that, if it occurs, has a favorable or negative impact on a project's goals. One cannot rely on the computers and hardware to be operational during the project's development. It's possible that the hard disk has suddenly crashed or that the motherboard has begun to fail. Even if there is no virus in the system, it is possible that the antivirus system will be breached and the virus will infiltrate the system, resulting in the destruction of key project files.

Keeping in mind such circumstances, it is preferable to make frequent backups of daily progress to an external hard drive. Simply saving a duplicate of each update in a secure location helps reduce the risk of losing everything in one swoop.

Another precaution to take is to set up an account on any cloud platform, such as OneDrive or GoogleDrive, and upload all the research materials and updated documents there to prevent losing them all at once. To avoid any danger, the document or software code should be published to the cloud platform after each update. The above measures were followed in the development of this project to avoid unforeseen situations.

Chapter 5. LEARNING POINTS

The main computational difficulty in robot games is evaluating who has a winning strategy between the players. In the 2-dimension VAS games to determine whether Eve(attacker) has a winning strategy for getting to the goal configuration from the base configuration, or if Adam(defender) can prevent the objective from being achieved is difficult. It was seen that the strategy was decidable in certain versions of the game. It has been seen during the development of the thesis that decision making is an important part of everyday life, and it is mostly comparable to the decision making in any game, to achieve the winning strategy. During the initial phase the previous research papers were crucial in understanding the fundamentals of how robot games must operate. It gave a clear understanding of the steps involved in developing different variations of the game in two dimension. Developing the algorithms from scratch for the different cases discussed has helped improved the approach for similar problems like this for future. The backtracking technique used to determine the winning strategy is something that was very new to implement. It was a new approach to tackle problems like this in an easy way to understand the fundamental. Also, in an industrial point of view it was seen that game theory plays a vital role in addressing questions for competitors in the same field to determine the winner in the market. They also require a winning strategy to stand out from the rest of the crowd which is inspired by robot games or rather game theory. The entire process of the thesis has helped developed understanding, investigating a substantial unknown problem in the domain of Computer Science. Effective time management and planned development by breaking the project into multiple steps of development and their reviews and feedbacks was also important for the success of the thesis.

Chapter 6. PROFESSIONAL ISSUES

The BCS Code of Conduct is a one-of-a-kind and significant validation of your integrity as well as an IT professional's code of ethics (2022). It specifies the traits shared as practitioners, dedicated about developing a healthy computing community, and it is maintained by all BCS member. The member of the organization has dedicated themselves since 1957 and are on a quest to make sure that everyone has a favorable experience with technology. By improving standards of competence and behavior across the IT sector and addressing the ethical difficulties one confronts along the road, BCS guarantee that the digital journey is secure and productive for everyone (2022). The code of conduct is based on four essential principles :

- ***You make IT for everyone***

In this thesis, I address the issue of undecidability in the second dimension of the robot game by creating subcases and making it available to everyone, regardless of gender or race, making it available to a wider society and wanting everyone to have access to it by submitting the project codes and documents to The University of Liverpool.

- ***Show what you know, learn what you don't***

At the commencement of the thesis, not everything was known. The basic understanding of how robot games are played and what techniques must be taken in the context of this thesis has been formed from reading from past research. It was a learning and growing process till the project's end date.

- ***Keep IT real. Keep IT professional. Keep IT on***

By citing all the works included in the bibliography, it is ensured that everyone gets their proper credit and that no conflicts develop. Providing all the necessary credits related to the development of the project.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A. CODE SNIPPETS AND OUTPUTS

A.1 Code for No Defender move:

For the project python3.3 was used, together with the pandas and numpy module. The code below demonstrates achieving the tree using backtracking approach for the attacker as discussed above.

```

1 import pandas as pd
2 import numpy as np
3
4 # defender_move = np.array(list(map(int, input("Enter attacker point ").split())))
5 attacker_move = np.array(list(map(int, input("Enter attacker point ").split())))
6 target_point = np.array([0,0])
7 attacker_winning_positions = []
8 attack_inv = attacker_move*-1
9 # defender_inv = defender_move*-1
10 attack_pos = attack_inv + target_point
11 attacker_winning_positions.append(np.array(attack_pos))
12 for i in range(5):
13     # print("in loop attack_pos,target_point ",attack_pos,target_point)
14     attack_pos_t = attack_pos + attack_inv
15     # print("attack_pos_t ",attack_pos_t)
16     attack_pos = attack_pos_t
17     # print("attack_pos ",attack_pos)
18     attack_pos_t = attack_pos_t + attack_inv
19     attacker_winning_positions.append(attack_pos)
20     # print("attack_pos_t_2nd ", attack_pos_t)
21 print("Winning positions ",np.array(attacker_winning_positions))
22

```

Outputs:

The below output shows the winning set of the attacker achieved using the backtracking approach for the input provided.

```
documents/COMP702/exp.py
Enter attacker point 1 2
Winning positions [[ -1 -2]
[ -2 -4]
[ -3 -6]
[ -4 -8]
[ -5 -10]
[ -6 -12]]
(base) soumyodiptamajumdar@Soumyodiptas-MacBook-Air ~ % /Users/soumy
documents/COMP702/exp.py
Enter attacker point 3 4
Winning positions [[ -3 -4]
[ -6 -8]
[ -9 -12]
[-12 -16]
[-15 -20]
[-18 -24]]
(base) soumyodiptamajumdar@Soumyodiptas-MacBook-Air ~ % /Users/soumy
documents/COMP702/exp.py
Enter attacker point 3 1
Winning positions [[ -3 -1]
[ -6 -2]
[ -9 -3]
[-12 -4]
[-15 -5]
[-18 -6]]
(base) soumyodiptamajumdar@Soumyodiptas-MacBook-Air ~ %
```